

Looking into the Thoughts of Parliamentarians on Libraries: An Analysis of Discussions During the 10th to 18th Lok Sabhas

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Abstract

The role of libraries and information centres has been crucial to the growth and progress of a developing nation like India, since information serves as the fuel of modern society. The Government of India is the highest authority for making decisions regarding various facets of development in the nation, and so the discussions in the Parliament of India—the legislative organ—have much value as they reflect the demands of the citizens of India and how the government responds to them. The research focuses on analyzing the discussions on the topic of libraries during the period of the 10th to 18th Lok Sabhas (1991-Present). The documented discussions have been collected from the Parliament Digital Library (<https://eparlib.sansad.in/>), which serves as the primary repository of parliamentary documents. Primary data related to the discussions, such as the questions on libraries and the answers to them, the Lok Sabha members (MPs) asking and answering those questions, the political parties they are affiliated with, *etc.*, have been collected and organized. A comprehensive Lok Sabha-wise and summarized data carpentry-based general analysis of the corpora have been done using OpenRefine. The text of the questions and answers has been analyzed using text analysis tools, namely Voyant and Distant Reader. Also, the Llama 3.1 8 billion (instant) Large Language Model (LLM) has been suitably prompted to categorise the discussions under respective logical themes. It has been observed that the average lengths of questions and answers increased with each successive Lok Sabha. As categorised by the LLM, the themes of the discussions were observed, and they covered a broad spectrum of focus, including government libraries, library science, *etc.* The Bharatiya Janata Party was involved in most of the discussions related to libraries during these Lok Sabhas, and MPs, namely Dr. Sukanta Majumder and Kumari Selja respectively asked and answered the highest number of questions. The current research may serve as a cornerstone for understanding what the parliamentarians discuss about libraries, because of the insights it provides. This research is open-ended, as the Indian legislative sessions continue to address national development and libraries are likely to remain a focus of deliberations given their societal value.

Keywords: Data Carpentry, Distant Reader, Large Language Models, Libraries, Parliament Digital Library, Parliament of India, Text Analysis, Voyant.

1. Introduction

The Government of India serves as the top-level authority for making decisions for the nation. In a developing mixed economy and a complex democracy like that of India, the government's decisions play a crucial role. The Constitution of India serves as a document embodying the way the Government of India works, the fundamental rights and duties of the citizens, the citizenship they hold, and much more (Avtonomov, 2024; Bhattacharjee, 2023;

Roy, 2024). Among everything, what the Constitution of India mentions is the right to education for all (Das, 2024). Accordingly, the government has played a big role in the fields of education and empowering innovations for a better future of the nation (Abhyankar, 2014; Borthakur *et al.*, 2024; Dutta, 2022; Puri, 2020). The Parliament of India serves as the supreme body of legislation. It is among the three pillars, alongside the people and the political parties, that hold the Indian democracy (Singh, 2025). It has its role in passing bills that are related to serving some

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1. Introduction

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(Das, 2024). Accordingly, the government has played a big role in the fields of education and empowering innovations for a better future of the nation (Abhyankar, 2014; Borthakur *et al.*, 2024; Dutta, 2022; Puri, 2020). The Parliament of India serves as the supreme body of legislation. It is among the three pillars, alongside the people and the political parties, that hold the Indian democracy (Singh, 2025). It has its role in passing bills that are related to serving some purpose and lead to the formation of acts. It is bicameral in nature, with both houses, the Lok Sabha and the Rajya Sabha, having their roles (Wikipedia Contributors, 2025). The Lok Sabha is the lower house consisting of representatives from different constituencies elected by the citizens of India. Hence, it houses a diverse group of members who may represent the needs of the people and propose development of various regions across the nation. As evident from the Lok Sabha sessions that took place over the years, the representatives have presented their views on the development of various matters. The discussions are mostly held with the purpose of triggering actions that would lead to the growth of the nation. The Parliament of India is the gateway through which the development of the nation is streamlined. To keep the discussions done in the Parliament of India transparent, they have been documented and provided for free access through the Parliament's digital library (<https://eparlib.sansad.in/>). It is a digital repository containing parliamentary documents. It plays an important role in informing users of how the legislation works. The Parliament digital library has evolved, and a separate interface for the digital library of the *Digital Sansad* available at <https://elibrary.sansad.in/>.

Libraries, as a social institution play an immense role in meeting the information needs of the member of the society (Granchak, 2014; Pleshkevich, 2024). Libraries have always played a role in empowering students pursuing their educational degrees, as well as lifelong learners. Since the world is going through an age of information, the role of libraries is more prevalent. While adopting modern technologies, libraries have upgraded themselves to better serve the right users with the right information at the right time. Libraries have been a nucleus around which the thoughts and initiatives of the government have revolved for a long time. The central and the state government have always taken steps to model and improve the way the national library and different public libraries work. Moreover, the academic libraries of the numerous institutions across India have also received their support. Various other initiatives, such as the development of information and communication technologies for libraries, library and information science education, as well as the recruitment of workforce to work in libraries have been taken across time (Adhikary & Vasudevan, 2014). Each Lok Sabha session has showcased the eagerness of the parliamentarians on the topic of libraries. To understand the way the government thinks and works for the development of libraries, it is important to understand the discussions done within the Lok Sabha, since they can serve as strong evidence of the demands on the development of libraries across the nation. One of the suitable ways to understand the discussions is to analyze the text to get valuable insights. This can be extensively achieved through modern text analysis techniques using different software.

2. Text Analysis of Parliamentary Discussions

Text has always been a valuable source of information, available in huge quantities as published literature of different forms with a broad range of provenance. However, in the past, unstructured texts were underutilized as valuable sources for data-driven insights because of their unstructured nature. Modern innovations have led to the emergence of techniques to analyze unstructured text, irrespective of the form. Text analysis, as evident from the term, involves techniques for analyzing textual data and extracting valuable information from it. It has been one of the booming areas of research, having a wide spectrum of applications (Ke *et al.*, 2024). The applications of modern advancements in information technologies and artificial

intelligence have led to innovations such as understanding the sentiment of textual data (sentiment analysis), topic modelling, n-gram analysis and many other techniques which make natural language textual data more suitable for use as information sources. With the increasing developments in language models and AI techniques, the field of text analysis is expected to have a long path of improvements and more efficient techniques.

The textual data on parliamentary discussions hold a lot of valuable information. These can be utilized to extract insights about the discussions, such as the average length of the questions and answers (discussions), the interrelationships between individual terms within the text, the frequency of usage of the different terms, and various other valuable information. Moreover, the other associated data obtained from the parliament's digital library holds information about the engagement of different parliamentarians, various political parties, *etc.* A comprehensive analysis of the parliamentary text would lead to an understanding of the thoughts of the Indian legislature and how the proposals for developments in libraries are put before the government.

3. Literature Review

The governance of this nation is bestowed upon the legislative, executive and judiciary systems. In his work, Singh (2025) mentions the three pillars of Indian democracy that help in shaping the growth of the nation, *i.e.*, the Parliament of India, the political parties, and the people of the nation. The role of the trinity is immense. The work emphasizes the role of the Parliament in representing the voice of the people of India, alongside its role as the legislative body of the government. In their research work, Chaurasia & Singh (2024) traced the journey of the development of public libraries in India. The work delves into the history of public libraries and the opportunities and challenges they face. They emphasised the vital role that the Government of India played in the development of public libraries. In his study, Saini (2011) dealt with the role the Government and the library authorities played in the implementation of library legislation in north-eastern India. The research work focused on a study of public libraries in Mizoram. The mentioned works show just a cross-section of the massive role the government plays in the development of libraries across the nation. Although there isn't any published research work on the Parliament of India's digital library, the impact that a similar digital library has on the people is well represented in other works, such as Campos *et al.* (2008), which demonstrated the usage of the parliamentary digital library of Andalusia.

Text analysis powers the process of understanding the discussions that have been done during the parliamentary sessions. Its importance lies in helping to understand facts and insights deeply from within the text that may not be easily perceived with manual rigor. The publication, (Ontotext, 2025), served as a cornerstone for understanding the basic idea of text analysis. According to the work, the process of text analysis involves extracting machine-readable information from unstructured text to support data-driven content management. It also stresses the importance of building customized text mining pipelines for achieving accuracy and overcoming the ambiguity of natural language. A distinct work, entitled "What is Text Analysis", GeeksforGeeks (2024) mentions the significance of text analysis techniques. Also termed as textual text mining or textual statistics evaluation, the importance of the technique is because of the increasing volume of text generated at every moment. This work also dives into the different text analysis techniques such as sentiment analysis, topic modelling, knowledge extraction, *etc.* Various research works have been done that demonstrate the application of text analysis techniques. Tausczik and Pennebaker (2010) review different computerized methods for text analysis. It describes LIWC, which is a transparent text analysis program counting words in psychologically meaningful categories. Suissa *et al.* (2021) state that although Deep

Neural Networks (DNNs) may serve as relevant technology in the task of text analysis and other tasks related to digital humanities, there are mainly two issues related to it: a lack of training data and the need for domain adaptation. They analyze use cases of digital humanities studies and propose a decision model for choosing appropriate deep learning approaches. For the purpose of effective text analysis, Yang *et al.* (2022) propose a supervised deep topic modelling approach. In this technique, they look forward to a technique of leveraging the auxiliary data related to text in order to enhance the discovery of latent topics within the text. Guo (2022) proposed DLSTA, which stands for Deep Learning-assisted Semantic Text Analysis. Its purpose is to use big data to detect human emotion. It can be done from textual data sources by using notions of NLP. Sengupta (2024) shows the application of natural language processing and supervised machine learning techniques in legislative text analysis. In the research, the process of text analysis was automated to identify applicable law sections from judicial case reports. Maitra *et al.* (2014) presented a novel text analysis platform for pharmacovigilance of clinical drugs that assists intelligent automation by integrating a medical language processing pipeline and causal reasoning chain. It worked on publicly available biomedical databases. Kairaitytė-Užupė *et al.* (2023) described the use of Voyant, an open-source text analysis software for analyzing text corpus of digital humanities. The analysis was performed on works indexed on the Web of Science and ScienceDirect databases. The work shows the support Voyant provided in finding important fields of research and other tasks, such as finding themes using distant reading and interactive reading techniques.

The given literature dives deep into the methods and importance of text analysis. These serve as helpful guides for working extensively with the text of the parliamentary discussions. But since the discussions may be associated with a lot of other valuable information, analyzing them is important and helpful for the sake of a lot of purposes. Mukhopadhyay *et al.* (2021) and Mukhopadhyay and Mitra (2021), in their research, described a group of data-driven techniques that can be used to transform how libraries work with their data, diving into the field of library carpentry. They explained various techniques using OpenRefine, an open-source data wrangling software. Using a handful of case studies, they explained the way bibliographic data can be effectively utilized. The significance of this research work is to acquaint users with the features of OpenRefine, which can also be used to analyze data associated with parliamentary discussions in a suitable way.

4. Research Gap

As evident from the literature review, various supporting works related to the impact of government on libraries, text analysis techniques, *etc.* are available. The literature review includes just a cross-section of the huge amount of available publications, some of which are also open access. Yet there isn't any work that shows the text analysis of Indian parliamentary documents. Understanding the discussions on libraries in the Parliament of India is vital because of the need to know how the government responds to the needs and demands by listening to the voice of the citizens of India. This gap in research availability triggers the current research, which looks forward to analyzing the discussions on libraries in the Parliament.

5. Research Objectives

The broad objective of the research is to comprehensively analyze discussions on the topic of libraries, held during the 10th to 18th Lok Sabhas. The aim is to analyze the recent discussions and to present insights from the data. The specific objectives of the research are :

- (a) To perform a general analysis of the participation of different members and political parties in the discussions during each Lok Sabha,
- (b) To understand the trend of the length of the members' questions and answers,
- (c) To use large language models to find out the themes of discussions during each Lok Sabha, and
- (d) To analyze the discussions using Voyant and Distant Reader.

6. Materials and Methods

The methodological strategy to collect, clean, and analyze the parliamentary discussions about libraries and their development is explained in this section. It demonstrates the data gathering process from the "Parliament Digital Library," how we prepare the dataset by using a data-transforming tool for text analysis, and lastly, how we analyze the dataset by using the text analysis tools.

6.1 Data Collection

The data related to the parliamentary discussions has been collected from the Parliament of India's digital library, which can be referred to at <https://eparlib.sansad.in/>. With appropriate field searching techniques, the discussions containing the term "library", during the 10th to 18th Lok Sabhas (specifically in Part-I), have been retrieved. The data contains various information such as the member who asked and answered the questions, the political party to which they are affiliated, the associated ministry, *etc.*, alongside the questions and answers. The data have been collected in a tabular form using a suitable spreadsheet software.

6.2 Tools Used for Analysis

The analysis of the discussions has been done using a two-fold approach. The first part is a data carpentry-based general analysis, and the second part is a thorough text analysis of the discussions.

In the first part, OpenRefine, which is an open-source data wrangling software, was used to clean and perform multifaceted operations on this tabular dataset. OpenRefine is selected because of its "AI extension," as this extension allowing integration of any LLM by using the Chat Completion URL, model name, and API key, and we also configure the model according to the type of task by changing the "Temperature" and "Top-K". For the topic analysis, we have integrated and utilized llama-3.1-8b-instant instead of a traditional approach like using Distant Reader. Distant Reader can perform topic modelling for the whole corpus or dataset, but using an LLM allows us to analyze the topic for individual question-answer pairs from parliaments. Specifically, this LLM is selected due to its "Tokens Per Minute (TPM)" and "Requests Per Minute (RPM)" features, which are 250K and 1K, and compared to other open-source LLMs, they are higher.

In the next phase, we used two open-source software, *i.e.*, Voyant and Distant Reader, for text analysis. Voyant is a Java-based package that runs locally and performs text analysis, while Distant Reader is a Python-based software that is used to build a carrel based on the text corpus and perform text analysis by creating a summary. From an array of text analysis tools, Voyant is selected because of its interactive visualization, as they are essential for identifying word frequency patterns and longitudinal trends; Distant Reader allows for calculating readability scores and analyzing n-grams like unigrams and bigrams, which provides a structural summary of the dataset in comparison to visual representation.

6.3 Steps of the Research

6.3.1 Data Carpentry-based Analysis

Using OpenRefine, the dataset of parliamentary discussions has been analyzed both Lok Sabha-wise as well as with the whole dataset. The respective columns that contained data about the members who asked and answered the most questions, and the political parties who did the same, were faceted and their occurrence counts were observed. Moreover, the column containing the names of questioners was observed to find the average number of members who asked the questions together. Using suitable GREL expressions and further external operations, the average lengths of the questions and answers were observed. An additional question-answer corpus was created for further theme analysis.

6.3.2 Categorization under Themes using LLM

The question-answer corpus was provided to the llama-3.1-8b-instant large language model, and it was suitably prompted to generate themes as well as respective sub-themes, if any. Here's the prompt that has been provided to the LLM:

“Read the question and categorise it based on the theme of the question asked in Indian Parliament like the name of the organisation and subfacets associated with it. Represent the category in the following manner -- Organisation--subtheme. If there are more than one subthemes, follow the same style but connect categories by \$\$ symbol. Give me only categories and do not provide any additional text.”

To mitigate this risk of hallucination, the research included a human verification layer in which a random 5% sample of the whole dataset, with LLM-generated themes, was verified by authors. This process confirmed the effectiveness of the model in capturing the essence of the parliamentary discussion.

6.3.3 Text analysis using Voyant

The dataset of discussions was uploaded to Voyant Server. It was able to generate different statistical data as well as visualizations related to the analyzed data. The software provides the ability to adjust the contents of the visualizations as per requirements.

6.3.4 Text Analysis using Distant Reader

Using suitable commands of Distant Reader, which is based on Python, the dataset of discussions was used to create a carrel. The carrel served as a base for further analysis that the software performed. The carrel was further processed to create a summarization which contained visualizations as well as data as results of the analysis.

7. Results and Observations

The following section of this article presents the empirical results from the multifaceted analysis of Indian parliamentary discussions about libraries. The findings of the analysis were divided into three categories: General statistical analysis, theme distribution using LLM, and structural and visual representations of Indian legislative discourse.

7.1 General Analysis

Upon performing the analysis using data carpentry, findings were obtained for each Lok Sabha. Table 1 demonstrates the Lok Sabha-wise observations.

Table 1. Lok Sabha-wise observations upon analysis using data carpentry

Lok Sabha	Member asking the highest number of questions	Political party asking the most number of questions	Avg. no. of questions	Member answering the most number of questions	Political party answering the most number of questions
10 th (1991-1996)	Chitta Basu	Indian National Congress	1.1406	Kumari Selja	Indian National Congress
11 th (1996-1997)	A. Siddaraju, George Fernandes, and others	Bharatiya Janata Party	1	S. R. Bommai	All India Progressive Janata Dal
12 th (1998-1999)	B. M. Mensinkai, Kariya Munda, and others	Communist Party of India (Marxist)	1	Dr. Murli Manohar Joshi	Bharatiya Janata Party
13 th (1999-2004)	Kolur Basavanagoud	Indian National Congress	1.2444	Ananth Kumar	Bharatiya Janata Party
14 th (2004-2009)	Mahavir Bhagora	Bharatiya Janata Party	1.3658	Ambika Soni	Indian National Congress
15 th (2009-2014)	Vikrambhai Arjabhai Maadam	Indian National Congress	1.4468	V. Narayanasamy	Indian National Congress
16 th (2014-2019)	Dr. Virendra Kumar, Sreeramulu B. and others	Bharatiya Janata Party	1.5645	Dr. Mahesh Sharma	Bharatiya Janata Party
17 th (2019-2024)	Dr. Sukanta Majumder	Bharatiya Janata Party	2.4761	G. Kishan Reddy	Bharatiya Janata Party
18 th (2024-Present)	Aparajita Sarangi, Daggumalla Prasada Rao, and others	Bharatiya Janata Party	1.5555	Gajendra Singh Shekhawat	Bharatiya Janata Party

From the data shown in Table 1, it can be inferred that, although other political parties participated in the discussions as well, the participation of Indian National Congress and Bharatiya Janata Party is more prevalent. It is also observed that the 17th Lok Sabha had the highest average number of questions. When the total dataset spanning across the 10th to 18th Lok Sabhas was analyzed, it was found that Dr. Sukanta Majumder asked the most number of questions, *i.e.*, 7, and members of the Bharatiya Janata Party were involved in asking the most questions, *i.e.*, 207. In terms of answering the questions, the lead was taken by Kumari Selja (44 answers) and the Bharatiya Janata Party (173 answers). Overall, an average of 1.4876 questioners were there spanning across the Lok Sabhas.

The average lengths of the questions and answers were observed for each Lok Sabha, and the results were observed as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Average lengths of questions and answers (words) during the Lok Sabhas

Lok Sabha	Average length of questions	Average length of answers
10 th (1991-1996)	306.7812	394.2187
11 th (1996-1997)	316.2857	468.5714
12 th (1998-1999)	350.2857	362.1428
13 th (1999-2004)	386.3333	754.3777
14 th (2004-2009)	376.8048	883.8780
15 th (2009-2014)	464.3404	884.4042
16 th (2014-2019)	535.4838	3245.7741
17 th (2019-2024)	532.2380	4539.1428
18 th (2024-Present)	519.2222	10661.2222
Overall	429.5833	1946.3919

Figure 1. Average lengths of questions and answers across the 10th-18th Lok Sabhas.

From Table 2 and Figure 1, the changes in the average length of questions and answers have been observed. The massive rise in the average length of the answers during the 18th Lok Sabha was due to the inclusion of large amounts of statistical data within them to support the answers. The overall average length of answers was greater than the questions. The significant rise in the average length of answers suggests better bureaucratic discourse and data-driven transparency.

This increase indicates that the recent parliamentarians are not only acknowledging but also providing comprehensive reports that contain statistical data and annexures to present a complete scenario of library developments. Because of the increasing volume and detail of data included in responses, automated text analysis techniques such as those employed in this study are increasingly necessary to make sense of parliamentary discussions at scale.

When properly prompted, the LLM was able to generate a set of themes for the discussions. Table 3 demonstrates the top 3 most discussed themes during the 10th to 18th Lok Sabhas. The top 3 generated themes were scanned by the researchers who are domain specialists in library and information science. They acted as reviewers of the accuracy of the LLM's results, and hence it mitigated the chances of some hallucinations that may occur from the LLM's side.

Table 3. Most discussed themes during the 10th to 18th Lok Sabhas, as predicted by LLM

Lok Sabha	Top discussed LLM-suggested themes (in descending order of coverage)	
10 th (1991-1996)	1	Library Committee - Pay Scales
	2	Library and Information Services in Central Libraries
	3	Library Science
11 th (1996-1997)	1	Department of Culture
	2	Council for Indian Cultural Relations - Missing Manuscripts
	3	Government of India - Department of Culture
12 th (1998-1999)	1	Delhi Public Library - Filling of Group 'D' Posts
	2	Department of Culture - Library Development
	3	Government of India - Culture
13 th (1999-2004)	1	Department of Culture - Libraries
	2	Asiatic Society Library Preservation
	3	Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) - Traditional Knowledge Digital Library
14 th (2004-2009)	1	CSIR - National Science Digital Library
	2	Archaeological Survey of India - Architectural Conservation
	3	Central Board of Secondary Education - Classroom Experience
15 th (2009-2014)	1	Library
	2	Ministry of Culture - Library Development
	3	AICTE - E-Learning & Digital Library
16 th (2014-2019)	1	Ministry of Culture - National Mission on Libraries
	2	Aligarh Muslim University Library Access
	3	Government Libraries
17 th (2019-2024)	1	Ministry of Culture - Libraries
	2	Ministry of Culture - National Mission on Libraries
	3	Government Libraries

18 th (2024-Present)	1	Ministry of Culture - National Mission on Libraries
	2	Government - National Digital Library
	3	Ministry of Culture - Libraries

According to the findings, it is observed that the discussions revolved around a wide range of topics.

7.2 Word Frequency Trends and Visualizations

When the set of discussions was uploaded to Voyant, it generated a handful of visualizations as well as statistics that help analyze the text. Voyant produced useful statistical data as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Basic statistical data about the text corpora as shown by Voyant

Parameter	Value
Total number of words	107,158
Total number of unique word forms	9,868
Vocabulary density	0.092
Average words per sentence	41.1

Additionally, it was shown that the top 3 most frequent terms are library (2446), libraries (1224) and state (896). Both of the top 2 terms are semantically similar, and just vary in number. These show that the discussions heavily discussed the topic of libraries during the conversations. The representation of the most frequent terms is also shown in Voyant using a visualisation called Cirrus. It represents each term in the text using different colours and sizes. The size of the terms in the Cirrus is directly proportional to the frequency of the term. Figure 2 shows the Cirrus representing the 100 most frequent terms within the text.

Figure 3. Trends of the top 5 most frequent terms across the different segments.

According to Figure 3, as usual, the most frequent term “library” both started and ended with the highest relative frequencies, except within the range between the 3rd and 5th segments, where the other frequent terms “libraries” and “national” overtook. Except for the term “national”, the other terms had the highest relative frequencies at the end segment, which represents the later Lok Sabhas in reality.

7.3 Structural Summary and Readability Analysis

The dataset analyzed on Distant Reader contained other related data alongside the questions and answers, such as the names of the political parties, names of members, *etc.* The summary generated by Distant Reader for the carrel provides important data related to the text. One of them is the readability score. It is a measure of the difficulty in reading the text. This metric, provided by Distant Reader, lies in the range [0, 100]. The lower the readability score, the tougher it is to read and understand, and the higher the value, the easier it is.

The readability score of the question-answer corpora is 50, which is in the middle of the range. This proves that the text is of moderate difficulty in reading. This measure serves as an important indicator of the difficulty in understanding the parliamentary discussions on libraries. Although the record of parliamentary discussions is accessible, citizens need a secondary-education level of literacy to understand the discussions. To increase the readability score, the policymakers may provide a simplified summary along with the technical reports or statistical data.

Distant Reader also represents the frequencies of n-grams within the text. An n-gram is an entity, where n represents the number of terms combined. Unigram represents single words, while bigram represents pairs of terms that occur together within the text. Bigrams are

the involvement of the different political parties, and the participation of the members in the discussions. This research, along with its positives, has been associated with some drawbacks. Firstly, the research methods didn't consider the Lok Sabhas of the past as well as the future. Hence, it isn't possible to represent the complete spectrum of the way the legislature thinks about libraries. This opens up the door to further research on Lok Sabha discussions on libraries in both the earlier and later Lok Sabhas.

Secondly, the usage of large language models in generating the themes for the discussions, although efficient and done with proper prompting, is not without limitations. Since the model itself hasn't been fine-tuned on Indian legislative or library-science-specific datasets, an inherent risk of "hallucination" may exist where the model generates plausible but incorrect themes. However, this study highlights that LLMs can be used as assistants in metadata generation or theme analysis but with domain-specific fine-tuning.

The role of the Government of India in every major decision has been there for long. Libraries, as the intellectual pillars of society, have much to offer, and the support of the government is much needed for the long term. The demands of the library staff as well as users must frequently reach the legislature through the questions raised by the political leaders in India. This would power the decisions the government takes for the development of libraries. The future of libraries lies in the hands of how the library professionals, researchers, authorities and technologies shape it, and the government must continue supporting them for the better.

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Author Contribution

Sneha Samanta : She is a former student of the Department of Library and Information Science, University of Kalyani. Her contributions to the current research include preparing the primary dataset for parliamentary conversations, using text analysis tools for getting valuable insights from the data, and preparing the research article. This research work is based on the dissertation work conducted for the fulfillment of her masters degree.

Madhumita Neogi : She is a Research Scholar at the Department of Library and Information Science, University of Kalyani. Her contribution to the research include guiding the first author in conducting the research, such as performing text analysis, LLM-based theme generation, analyzing the findings of the research, and conducting literature review.

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